

TE | SF

Transforming Education
for Sustainable Futures

CALL TO ACTION

Education for
Sustainable
Livelihoods

JULY 2023

THE CHALLENGE

There are many barriers to economic participation for the marginalised, and vocational education is a marginalised topic.

Transformative education interventions are needed to expand the status and scope of vocational education for decent, sustainable work.

Across the TEF Network, there were several projects focussing on Education for Sustainable Livelihoods worked on vocational preparation for decent, sustainable work. This included community education and social learning alongside formal education, TVET and training.

Projects found that vocational education and training is a marginalised topic, often considered inferior to formal education, and is often inaccessible to socially excluded communities who need the skills and training to transition to sustainable livelihoods.

Sites of learning are incredibly important for the purpose of inclusivity, and include spaces such as community centres, gardens, digital spaces, kitchens, and most notably under a tree.

Commonalities across all projects included a consideration of the barriers to economic participation and creating sustainability consciousness through learning.

Research participants were from the underserved, the vulnerable and those at an economic disadvantage. The research projects gave them a voice.

WHAT NEEDS TO BE TAKEN SERIOUSLY

... evidence informed **recommendations** for transformative education that can **strengthen sustainable livelihoods**

Skills for employability

Projects found that to support skills for employability, there is need to give adequate attention to the lived experience of those involved. Several projects focused on developing skills for employability for historically disadvantaged groups with valuable lessons emerging for transformative education that can support sustainable livelihoods.

For example

One Rwandan project focused on exploring the **lived experiences of Rwandan girls and women** not in employment, education and training, while another explored **skills development** for work readiness and youth employability. While both projects examined skills for employability and found that the training provided to young people in Rwanda does not enable them to obtain “decent work”, the solutions offered differed based on the lived experiences of the groups of people. Projects found that to determine the strategies needed to empower young people, including young women, one needs to understand their lived experience and accordingly adapt the education intervention based on this to empower them individually and allow them to achieve sustainable livelihoods. Similarly, in India, one project examined the ways in which students in smaller towns move between education and employment, what it means to be educated in a small town which is undergoing rapid growth, and the experiences of marginalised communities.

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Life skills for sustainable futures

Education for sustainable livelihoods requires that we also give attention to life skills for sustainable futures that complement technical skills associated with particular areas of practice. Life skills.

For example

A project in **South Africa** focused on developing a **framework for collective community-level economic solutions** in Makhanda which examined how local actors can work collectively to develop ecologically and socially responsible economic agency among the youth, to improve sustainable livelihoods and enhance household income security. This involved various engagements including building local agency for change, confidence of young people to hold local agencies accountable and to express themselves.

Similarly, young women in **Rwanda**, who are part of a co-operative who weave and create home decor, were equipped with digital and entrepreneurial skills to help them increase their income, and scale up their livelihoods.

Studies also found that building economic agency is a collective social process, it is not just an individualised activity. This has implications for how enterprise education / entrepreneurship education programmes are designed.

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Education and Indigenous Livelihoods

Several projects examined ways in which indigenous communities are excluded from education and the ways in which the mainstream marginalises vocational learning.

For example:

Research undertaken in **India** investigated the issues of educational constructs in relation to the education of Adivasis. Their research, which included school children and adult learners, highlighted the way in which several Adivasi communities feel alienated within mainstream education as it fails to accommodate their diversity of needs and aspirations. Their research felt the need to claim sites of learning beyond the classroom, including the Adivasi worldview, which understands the purpose of education as one that enables youth to navigate the modern world and their home worlds. It recommended creating channels of learning across the academic and traditional Adivasi knowledge forms, which strengthen intergenerational ties and allow the young to acquire leadership skills.

Similarly, a number of projects in **the Horn of Africa** co-produced numeracy and literacy content on climate action using indigenous/ community knowledge. Another project enabled minority groups to improve their livelihoods, for example using numeracy skills to assist minority workers and informal traders to create lending programs, and increase access to finance.

CALL TO ACTION

What we ALL need to do TOGETHER ...

EVERYONE has a role to play in co-creating education for sustainable futures for ALL in ways that can strengthen sustainable livelihoods...

What role are you [can you] playing?

Education and training can support agency for sustainable livelihoods - A call to action

For Researchers: Encourage research *with* communities whose livelihoods are threatened. Create sustainable solutions for the root causes of unsustainability. Conceptualise sustainable livelihoods from the perspectives of those who are excluded from the mainstream narrative.

For Educators and Teachers: Create vocational programs that adapt existing skills, allowing vulnerable communities to transition to sustainable livelihoods. Democratise knowledge by ensuring inclusivity and participation in the decision-making processes that affect their livelihoods, and a greater engagement with adult vocational programmes.

For Policy Actors: Recognise the importance of and invest in vocational programs that address sustainable livelihoods, as these are often sidelined for mainstream education programs.

For Engaged Activists: Contextualise the sustainability agenda, by using indigenous and local knowledge to reframe 'Western' concepts of sustainable livelihoods. This could ensure greater inclusivity and inform awareness-raising campaigns.

We all have a role to play. What role can YOU play in advancing education for sustainable futures in ways that advance education for sustainable livelihoods?

THANK YOU!!

visit: <https://tesf.network/>

This CALL TO ACTION, compiled by Amal Ali with Poonam Batra, Heila Lotz-Sisitka and Michael Tusiime based on the findings of 67 co-engaged research projects implemented across 4 countries in the Transforming Education for Sustainable Futures Network involving India, Rwanda, South Africa and Somalia/Somaliland. Overall co-ordination was supported by the University of Bristol and partners, with UKRI with GCRF funding. It was complemented by substantive in-kind support and collegial relations that contributed significantly to the project's outcomes and success through intellectual, social, economic, ethical and other contributions.